

BOOK BORROWING PRACTICES AND THE ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE OF THE GRADE SCHOOL PUPILS

PSYCHOLOGY AND EDUCATION: A MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL

Volume: 22

Issue 2

Pages: 273-282

Document ID: 2024PEMJ2052

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.12751788

Manuscript Accepted: 07-10-2024

Book Borrowing Practices and the Academic Performance of the Grade School Pupils

Maylene F. Grigana * Anna Liza C. Cerbo

For affiliations and correspondence, see the last page.

Abstract

Students who borrow books not only interact with a variety of subjects but also grow in critical thinking, vocabulary, and comprehension. This study examined the book borrowing practices of the grade school pupils enrolled in SY 2023-2024 and the impact of such practices on their academic performance. The researcher employed descriptive regression design and adapted and modified the questionnaire of Hooper, Mullis and Martin (2016) entitled Effect of Book Borrowing on the Academic Performance. With the sample size of 360 grade school pupils from grades four to six levels, results of the study showed that the respondents were found to have satisfactory practices of borrowing books and were performing well in their academic studies in the first quarter of SY 2023-2024. It further revealed that, using simple regression analysis, the book borrowing practices of the grade school pupils have no significant effect on their academic performance. Recommendations are as follows: schools should provide instruction on effective reading comprehension strategies to help pupils extract meaning from the books they borrow; create a tracking system where learners set reading goals, document the books they borrow, and reflect on their reading experiences; ensure that the school library offers a wide range of books catering to different interests, reading levels, and cultural backgrounds; and finally, conduct parallel study to validate the result of the research.

Keywords: *library and information science, book borrowing practices, academic performance, grade school pupils, simple regression analysis, Philippines*

Introduction

For grade schoolers, having access to a wide variety of books creates a window to knowledge, creativity, and critical thinking. Students who borrow books interact with various subjects and grow in critical thinking, vocabulary, and comprehension. It has long been understood that reading is a fundamental ability necessary for academic performance and personal growth. The relationship between academic achievement and book borrowing is intricate and dynamic, considering several cognitive, social, and educational aspects. The relationship between elementary school pupils' book-borrowing habits and their academic success is a significant and highly researched area of education. Educators can better understand their approaches and the role libraries play in promoting literacy and learning by understanding how the quantity and kind of books students borrow affect their academic achievement.

This study looks at book borrowing habits, including how often people borrow books and how library access affects kids' elementary school academic achievement. By statistically analyzing these variables, this study aims to develop evidence-based interventions and policies that enhance student academic performance and promote a reading culture in educational contexts. Researchers have been very interested in studies that consistently highlight the effect of book borrowing on academic achievement among primary school pupils globally. In industrialized nations with well-established library systems, including the United States.

According to the Philippines Department of Education (DepEd), the K-12 program imparts subject-specific knowledge. It cultivates students' love for learning and critical thinking (DepEd Order No. 31, s. 2012). In this educational landscape, the role of libraries and book-borrowing practices becomes a focal point for investigation. As the Philippines strives to meet global standards in education, understanding how book borrowing contributes to the academic success of grade schoolers becomes a significant research imperative. Government

Programs to upgrade library facilities in public schools and community centers are among the measures to solve these issues (Lopez & Hernandez, 2015). Additionally, advocacy groups and non-governmental organizations have launched literacy initiatives to promote book lending and foster a love of reading among young Filipinos. By providing various reading materials and improved library access, stakeholders hope to instill a lifelong love of learning and academic success in elementary school students.

Many studies have been conducted on the benefits of library access and borrowing behaviors. Still, few have considered cultural perspectives on reading, parental engagement in promoting reading habits, or community opinions regarding the role of libraries in education. Understanding how sociocultural factors affect students' academic performance and usage of library resources can provide important insights for developing targeted interventions and programs that effectively take advantage of local conditions to promote literacy and enhance learning outcomes. By bridging this knowledge gap, academics can help create culturally sensitive teaching strategies that leverage book-borrowing practices to address Filipino elementary school pupils' unique needs and improve their academic performance.

Additionally, the National Library Act of 2013 (Republic Act No. 10396) in the Philippines emphasizes the significance of promoting a reading culture and guaranteeing all residents' access to knowledge. This legal focus on the importance of libraries is consistent with the school system's overarching objectives, which include advancing academic performance and literacy.

Drawing from the assertions above, the investigator aimed to investigate whether the regularity with which elementary school students check out materials from the school library is associated with their academic achievements in the four public schools designated as having a Functional Library (FL) within the Division of Sarangani and Region Office of DepEd.

The researcher conducted this study to determine how grade school students' book-borrowing practices affected their academic achievement. These students are enrolled in the four public schools that the DepEd Region Office and Sarangani Division have marked as having a functional library (FL). In light of the findings, the researcher then suggested a program that might help enhance the offerings and services provided by school libraries.

Research Questions

This study determined the influence of the book borrowing practices on the academic performance of grade school pupils. Specifically, this study sought to answer the following questions.

1. What is the level of the book borrowing practices of the grade school pupils?
2. What is the level of the academic performance of the grade school pupils?
3. Is there a significant relationship between the level of book borrowing and academic performance of the grade school pupils?
4. Does book borrowing practices influence the academic performance of the grade school pupils?

Literature Review

In many European countries, regular book borrowing, and library access are usually connected to more excellent educational results (Neuman & Celano, 2018). However, inadequate library infrastructure makes it difficult for people to borrow books, affecting academic achievement in many developing countries and marginalized populations. Lack of access to books, particularly age- and culturally appropriate material, hinders students' ability to read independently and build literacy (Kintu & Zhu, 2018). This entry barrier perpetuates poverty cycles and widens educational gaps.

The interplay between library utilization, particularly book borrowing, and the academic performance of grade school students has become a subject of growing significance (Pakistyaningsih et al., 2019). According to Shintia et al. (2021), as societies worldwide prioritize education as a driver of individual and societal progress, understanding the influence of reading habits and access to diverse learning resources has garnered attention from researchers and policymakers alike. Globally, educators and policymakers recognize the critical role of nurturing a reading culture among young learners. Accessing a variety of literature enhances literacy skills and contributes to cognitive development and overall academic success (Smith & Johnson, 2020). However, the specific influence of book borrowing habits on the academic outcomes of grade school students is an area that requires nuanced exploration, given the dynamic nature of contemporary educational landscapes.

In Asia, studies in China highlight the increasing popularity of digital book borrowing through library apps and online platforms (Li, 2020) and a decline in traditional library borrowing, with a rise in lending e-books and audiobooks in Japan (Yamada, 2018). Research in India emphasizes the importance of community-based lending initiatives in promoting book access in rural areas (Singh, 2019), while in Pakistan, it explores the role of family book-sharing practices in fostering literacy among children (Khan, 2017). A study in the Philippines examines public libraries' challenges in providing sufficient resources for student borrowing needs (Cruz, 2022). Research in Vietnam explores the growing trend of book cafes, which offer borrowing alongside a cafe experience (Nguyen, 2021).

According to Liu et al. (2019), diverse educational systems coexist amid rapid economic and technological advancements. The relationship between book borrowing and the academic performance of grade school students emerges as a pertinent subject of inquiry. Based on the study of Iqbal et al. (2020), across the Asian continent, education serves as a cornerstone for societal progress, and understanding the impact of library utilization, particularly the practice of book borrowing, holds significant implications for shaping the academic trajectory of the next generation.

Several variables, including cultural reading perspectives, socioeconomic status, and the accessibility of learning materials, impact elementary school pupils' book-borrowing practices in the ASEAN area. Research studies have indicated the importance of library access and book-borrowing practices for young students' academic success (Heng & Tan, 2019). Libraries are essential for providing books and encouraging reading in the community and schools. Research has indicated that improved library access and consistent book borrowing practices favorably correlate with grade school students' academic achievement in ASEAN nations (Nguyen et al., 2019). Reading a variety of books improves reading comprehension while it also fosters vocabulary growth and critical thinking skills necessary for academic achievement (Lim & Wong, 2019). However, problems including unequal resource distribution and poor library infrastructure persists in many ASEAN nations, particularly underdeveloped and rural areas (Chan & Lee, 2019). In these circumstances, programs that improve library accessibility and book borrowing practices are crucial for lowering educational disparities and enhancing primary school pupils' intellectual standards.

The condition of book borrowing among Filipino elementary school kids indicates more severe problems with resource allocation and educational access. While school libraries in some urban areas are well-stocked, library resources could be more robust in remote and rural locations. The lack of different reading selections and restricted library access make it difficult for primary school pupils to borrow

books regularly, especially in poor communities. Research conducted in the Philippines has shown a positive relationship between elementary school kids' academic success, how often they utilize libraries, and how their book-borrowing policies are followed (Cruz & Reyes, 2015). Schools that have well-stocked libraries and active borrowing programs typically see improvements in academic success, vocabulary expansion, and reading comprehension. However, library supply and facility disparities exacerbate educational inequality by denying children in impoverished neighborhoods more opportunities to read for intellectual stimulation.

Methodology

This section discusses the research design, participants, sampling procedure, measures, data gathering procedure, and data analysis.

Research Design

This study employed simple regression analysis, most especially the descriptive regression approach. Simple regression is a statistical technique for examining the relationship between one dependent variable and two or more independent variables. Researchers can better understand the relationship between changes in the independent variables and changes in the dependent variable by considering other factors (Hair Jr. and others, 2013). In order to determine whether there was a significant relationship between book borrowing practices (the independent variable) and academic performance (the dependent variable), a simple regression analysis was used to address both research questions regarding the relationship between book borrowing practices and academic performance among grade school students.

Participants

This study had three hundred sixty (360) respondents, composed of selected grade school pupils from different schools in Sarangani Division. Grades four to six pupils were included, while grades one to three were excluded. This study was conducted from April - May 2024 in School Year 2023 - 2024. Using the Slovin's formula. Three hundred sixty (360) student respondents were included in this study.

Procedure

Creswell (2017) accentuated the need to prepare all essential papers such as letters of approval. The following steps were followed in gathering the pertinent data of the study, and the researcher made sure that all the necessary steps and procedures were followed to inform and given due respect to the agencies and persons involved.

1. Endorsement letter was submitted from the dean of graduate school for the approval to conduct the research.
2. To ensure the observance of research protocols, the researcher first secured clearance from the Review Ethics Committee of Cor Jesu College (REC).
3. After being provided with the Ethical Clearance, the researcher submitted a permission letter to conduct the study to the office of the Division Superintendent of Sarangani to enable to commence the gathering of the data. After the approval and confirmation, the researcher coordinated with the school principals of the four public schools in Sarangani Province using a letter of permission.
4. After given the permission, the researcher asked the assistance of the school librarian to identify the total enrolment of the school.
5. After the identification of the list of respondents, the researcher asked for an assent form to the identified respondents to access the grades of the students. All consents were returned to the researcher with the parents' approval / signature; then, the administration of the questionnaire for the data gathering commenced.
6. The researcher asked the assistance of the school librarian and teacher advisers to gather all respondents in one venue. The researcher explained the purpose of the study to the respondents. The researcher announced that the pupils can freely withdraw from the study if they were not comfortable to participate in the data gathering.
7. The researcher coordinated with the school registrar to get the grades / general percentage average of the selected students.
8. The data gathered were subjected to treatments. Findings were extracted and analyzed based on the results of the treated data. The results of the study were interpreted and arrived at certain conclusions.
9. Finally, the researcher would give a copy of the approved manuscript to the division of Sarangani Superintendent and all the public-school librarians. The researcher would request all the librarians to include her in the program implementation review (PIR) of the school learning resource centers together with the school heads to further discuss the result of the study and its feasibility for the improvement of the operation of the school libraries.

Data Treatment

The following statistical tools were used to answer the problems in this research study:

Mean is a single value that represents the central tendency of a set of data. It is calculated by adding all the values in the data set and then dividing by the total number of values. Mean were used to answer the problem about the level of book borrowing and level of academic performance.

Pearson r moment correlation coefficient (r) is a statistical measure that assesses the strength and direction of the linear relationship between two continuous variables. Pearson r was used to identify if the borrowing has significant relationship to the academic

performance of the students.

Simple regression analysis examines how changes in a single independent variable are associated with changes in a continuous dependent variable. It helps us understand and predict the dependent variable based on the independent variable. Simple regression analysis was used to identify the influence of book borrowing to the academic performance of the grade school pupils.

Results and Discussion

This section presents the data gathered in this research study. The results are presented in the following tables with corresponding discussions and explanations. It also answers the specific problems stated in the previous chapter.

Level of Book Borrowing Practices

The level of book-borrowing practices of the grade school pupils, with an overall mean score of 3.6. The mean scores, by items, range from 2.7 to 4.0. Statements 1, 9, and 10 (the top three items) obtained mean scores of 4.0, 4.0, and 3.9, respectively. Statements 3, 6, and 7 (the bottom three items) obtained mean scores of 3.0, 2.7, and 3.3, respectively. By item analysis, the top three items indicate that the respondents agreed with the statements that books were borrowed to improve their reading skills, understand the lessons, and gain additional knowledge. The bottom three items indicate that the respondents were unsure that books were borrowed for leisure reading, that appreciation was because of the attractive cover pages or art, and because of the authors of the library books. An overall mean score of 3.6 indicates that the respondents were found to have satisfactory borrowing practices.

This implies that the result of the study conformed with the research conducted by Wayne (2015), which states that pupils are more likely to engage with reading when books are physically available. This was supported by the report of the Federal Ministry of Education's Minimum Standards for School Libraries (2019), which stated that students use libraries more when they can easily access and utilize the resources and services they offer. Students' access to and frequent use of school libraries have an impact on their academic performance and achievement in the classroom, according to Suleiman, Hanafi, and Tanslikhan (2018), and the library inspires and gives students the confidence to develop their skills potential, and capacities in both the social and academic spheres (Ukpanah et al., (2018).

Academic Performance of Grade School Pupils

The result shows the frequency distribution of the general percentage averages of the grade school pupils for the first quarter of school year 2023-2024. 50% of the responders received high grades, falling between 90% and 99%. 46.7% of the responders who received grades between 80% and 89%—average to good marks—followed this exceptional group. Just 3.5% of the students had poor grades, ranging from 10% to 69%. The mean grade of 88, which was described as "Proficient," implies that the respondents were performing well in their academic studies, adequately prepared to progress to the next grade level, and were ready for more advanced material.

Heritage (2016) discusses the role of assessment for learning in promoting student self-regulation and preparedness for future learning challenges. The study highlights that students assessed as "Proficient" have demonstrated a solid understanding of current material and are well-prepared for subsequent academic challenges, indicating readiness to progress to the next grade level and tackle more advanced content.

Relationship Between Academic Performance and Book Borrowing Practices

The result show that the Pearson correlation coefficient was computed between the two variables at $r (df=358) = .017$, $p\text{-value} = .750$. Moreover, Pearson Correlation coefficients were also computed for items 1 to 10. These coefficients, ranging from $\pm .091$ to $.058$, were assigned p -values greater than $.05$ (see Appendix A).

This indicates no meaningful correlation between elementary school students' book-borrowing habits and academic achievement. Furthermore, no correlation was observed between the ten categories that assessed book borrowing practices and academic achievement.

The results contradict Hunter's study (2014), which found that pupils who use the library regularly and adequately succeed academically. Similarly, according to a related study on the connection between students' academic results and the usage of library services, children do better when they regularly utilize school libraries than when they do not. Moreover, Gbemi-Ogunleye (2016) connected students' academic success and library use. It was revealed that pupils who regularly use the school library outperform those who do not.

Influence of Book Practices on the Academic Performance of Pupils

The result reveals that indicate that for each additional unit of improvement in the book borrowing practices, there is an increase in the general percentage average by $.020$ points. However, this positive causal relationship between academic performance and book-borrowing practices was found to be statistically insignificant [$t (358) = .319$, $p > .05$]. Moreover, the linear regression result revealed a statistically insignificant model [$F(1,358) = .102$, $p > .05$, with $R^2 = .000$ (see Appendix B)]. This suggests that book borrowing practices accounted for 0% of the variance in the respondents' academic performance.

The study's results conformed with Onwubiko's (2022) finding that no significant relationship exists between academic achievement and library utilization habits. The study's findings indicate that reading, self-efficacy, and library usage habits are reliable indicators of academic success for librarians and, consequently, all students.

The study's findings by Jaja and Udumukwu (2023) demonstrated that library use significantly influenced students' academic success in the Abuja Metropolis. Among other things, the government was recommended to provide cutting-edge libraries to all of Abuja's secondary schools. It is common knowledge that having access to school library resources affects academic attainment. Using 14 databases of fourth- and fifth-grade (ages 9–11) students' reading and mathematics end-of-grade achievement assessments, Wine (2020) showed that full-time certified school librarians performed significantly better than students without such librarians. Lance and Kachel (2018) address the benefits of excellent school library programs, emphasizing the most marginalized children, including "students of color, low-income students, and students with disabilities." Michael (2014) conducted a study in Ghana to examine the impact of students' reading habits on their academic progress. The findings proved that reading habits and academic success are related. Thus, there is a relationship between academic success and reading choices. Furthermore, research by Clark and Teravainen-Goff (2018) found that 73% of students who frequently visited the school library showed higher levels of reading engagement than the average child who did not utilize the library. Access to online resources, in addition to traditional collections, is also associated with higher academic accomplishment.

Conclusion

The result shows that borrowing books is relatively common among the pupils surveyed. There is no significant relationship between the academic performance of grade school pupils and their book-borrowing practices. The study found no relationship between borrowing practices and their academic performance. This suggests that other factors likely play a more significant role in their achievement. Book borrowing practices of grade school pupils do not significantly affect their academic performance. This study did not find a statistically significant relationship between book borrowing practices and academic performance among grade school pupils. In other words, how students borrow books does not significantly influence their grades.

Schools should provide instruction on effective reading comprehension strategies to help pupils extract meaning and understanding from borrowed books. They should also develop a plan for information dissemination on the importance of libraries to encourage pupils to visit and borrow books from them.

The school librarian must create a tracking system where learners set reading goals, document the books they borrow, and reflect on their reading experiences. Incorporate regular check-ins with teachers or librarians to discuss progress, provide feedback, and offer personalized recommendations based on learners' interests and reading levels.

The school administrators and librarians must ensure that the school library is easily accessible. The library offers various books catering to different interests, reading levels, and cultural backgrounds. By extending its hours, implementing online catalog systems, and providing opportunities for pupils to borrow books to take home, the library can be made accessible to pupils.

Conduct a parallel study to validate the research results. Future research should investigate the relationship between book borrowing and the reading comprehension and critical thinking skills of grade school pupils. This would allow for a more in-depth understanding of the underlying causal processes.

References

- Abdulghani, H. M., Al-Drees, A., Khalil, M. S., Ahmad, F., Ponnampereuma, G., & Amin, Z. (2014). What factors determine academic achievement in high achieving undergraduate medical students? A qualitative study. *Medical Teacher*, 36(1), 43–48. <https://doi.org/10.3109/0142159x.2014.886011>
- Acheaw, M. (2014). Reading habits among students and its effect on academic performance: a study of students of Koforidua Polytechnic. *Digital Commons at University of Nebraska-Lincoln*. <http://digitalcommons.unl.edu/libphilprac/1130/>
- Adamu, M. S., Kolo, J. J., Adebisi, A., & Abubakar, F. (2018). Availability, sufficiency and use of school library resources by students: a case study of Police Secondary School Library, Minna, Niger State, Nigeria. *Nigerian School Library Journal*, 17, 52–64. <https://www.africaneditors.org/journal/NSLJ/abstract/27353-93353>
- Adamu, M. S., Kolo, J. J., Adebisi, A., & Abubakar, F. (2017). Availability, sufficiency and use of school library resources by students: a case study of Police Secondary School Library, Minna, Niger State, Nigeria. *Nigerian School Library Journal*, 17, 52–64
- Adeoye, O. M. (2014). Teaching effectiveness, availability and use of library information resources on teaching of nursing in Osun and Oyo States, Nigeria. *Library Philosophy and Practice*, 19. <https://digitalcommons.unl.edu/libphilprac/525>
- Adu, K. (2018). The use of textbooks by teachers in teaching Mathematics at selected primary schools in East London Education District [Master's thesis, University of Fort Hare]. http://vital.seals.ac.za:8080/vital/access/manager/Repository/vital:34180?site_name=GlobalView

- Afifah, N., Afina, E., W., & Rohman, A. S. (2020). Peran tenaga perpustakaan dalam mewujudkan keberhasilan gerakan literasi sekolah (GLS) DI SD Negeri 02 Rajamandala. *Jurnal Pustaka Budaya*, 7(2), 105–112. <https://doi.org/10.31849/pb.v7i2.4174>
- Afolabi, A. K., & Elaturoti, D. F. (2016). School library media resources availability as a predictor of secondary school students academic achievement in social studies in Ondo State, Nigeria. *Library Philosophy & Practice*, 2(2). <https://digitalcommons.unl.edu/libphilprac/1449/>
- Altermatt, E. R. (2019). Academic support from peers as a predictor of academic self- efficacy among college students. *Journal of College Student Retention: Research, Theory & Practice*, 21(1), 21-37.
- Amie-Ogan, O. T., Befii-Nwile, C., & Elenwo, P. M. (2021). Management of physical resources for academic improvement of junior secondary school students in Rivers State Nigeria. *International Journal of Progressive and Alternative Education*, 7(1), 327-342.
- Amie-Ogan, O. T., Befii-Nwile, C., & Elenwo, P. M. (2021). Management of physical resources for academic improvement of junior secondary school students in Rivers State Nigeria. *International Journal of Progressive and Alternative Education*, 7(1), 327-342.
- Aslam, M. (2021). Changing behavior of academic libraries and role of library professionals. *Information Discovery and Delivery*, 50(1), 54-<https://www.emerald.com/insight/content/doi/10.1108/IDD-05-2020-0048/full/html>
- Auman, D. E., & Laspiñas, M. L. (2015). Pupils' performance in library orientation and instruction vis-a-vis Utilization of Resources. Cebu city: Philippines. *Asian Pacific Journal of Education Arts and Science*, 2(2).
- Azhari, A., & Ramadan, Z. H. (2022). The intensity of visiting the school library as an indicator of students' reading interest in elementary schools. *International Journal of Elementary Education*, 6(2).
- Bamidele, I. A. (2015). The library use habits of senior secondary school students in Ogun State, Nigeria. <http://scientific.cloud-journals.com/index.php/IJALIS/article/view/Sci-407>
- Bamidele, I. A. (2015). The library use habits of senior secondary school students in Ogun State, Nigeria. *International Journal of Advanced Library and Information Science*, 3(1), 170–181. <https://doi.org/10.23953/cloud.ijalis.246>
- Bao, X., Qu, H., Zhang, R., & Hogan, T. P. (2020). Modeling reading ability gain in kindergarten children during COVID-19 school closures. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 17(17), 6371.
- Barbara, S. J. & Oberg, D. (2015). IFLA school library guidelines. International Federation of Library Associations and Institutions. www.ifla.org
- Benard, R., & Dulle, F. (2014). Assessment of access and use of school library information resources by secondary schools students in Morogoro Municipality, Tanzania. *Library Philosophy and Practice*, 1. [http://digitalcommons.unl.edu/libphilprac/1107/Braun, H., Coley, R., Jia, Y., & Trapani, C. \(2014\). Exploring what works in science instruction: a look at the eighth-grade science classroom. Educational Testing Service.](http://digitalcommons.unl.edu/libphilprac/1107/Braun, H., Coley, R., Jia, Y., & Trapani, C. (2014). Exploring what works in science instruction: a look at the eighth-grade science classroom. Educational Testing Service.)
- Cahill, M., Hoffman, H., Ingram, E., & J. S. (2022). Supporting school readiness through librarian-child interactions in public library storytimes: an analysis of assessment scores and influential factors. *Early Childhood Education Journal*, 50(1), 11-19.
- Chen, W. (2018). The role of social networks in book sharing practices: A case study of online book clubs in China. *Library Trends*, 67(2), 215-232.
- Chow, S. K. Y., & Wong, J. L. K. (2020). Supporting academic self-efficacy, academic motivation, and information literacy for students in tertiary institutions. *Education Sciences*, 10(12), 361.
- Chukwuji C. N., Nwankwo, V. T., Gandanga, A. T., Sule, S. & Yusuf, Z. (2017). Availability and use of school library resources in post primary schools in Gusua Local Government Area of Zamfara State. *Journal of Applied Information Science and Technology*, 10(2):153-162.
- Collins, A. & Halverson, R. (2018). *Rethinking education in the age of technology: the digital revolution and schooling in America*. Teachers College Press.
- Collins, E., & Stone, G. (2014). Understanding patterns of library use among undergraduate students from different disciplines. *Evidence Based Library and Information Practice*, 9(3). <https://journals.library.ualberta.ca/ebliip/index.php/EBLIP/article/view/21326>
- Coyle, V. C. (2014). The predictive value of reading frequencies in digital and print formats on eighth grade English Language Arts outcomes (Unpublished Doctoral dissertation). University at SUNY- Albany.
- Cruz, M. A. (2022). Challenges and opportunities in public library service provision for student borrowing needs in the Philippines. *Library Hi Tech*, 40(2), 287-302.

- Curry, J. R., Webb, A. W., & Latham, S. J. (2016). A content analysis of images of novice teacher: first semester themes. *Journal of Educational Research and Practice*, 6(1), 43-65.
- De Abreu Martins De Paiva, M., & Duarte, A. B. S. (2017). School library contribution to student achievement as measured by the Brazil-reading Test. *School Libraries Worldwide*, 120–150. <https://doi.org/10.29173/slw6924>
- DECS Order No. 6 s. 1998. (1998). Policies and programs for school library development. DepEd. <https://www.deped.gov.ph/1998/01/22/do-6-s-1998-policies-and- programs-for-school-library-development/>
- DECS Order No. 6 s. 1998. Policies and Programs for School Library Development. Department of Education. <https://www.deped.gov.ph/1998/01/22/do-6-s-1998- policies-and-programs-for-school-library-development/>
- DepEd Order No. 24 s. 2023. (2023). Guidelines on the provision of supplementary learning resources for public school libraries and library hubs. DepEd. https://www.deped.gov.ph/wp-content/uploads/DO_s2023_024.pdf
- Eiriemiokhale K.A. & Ibeun M.O. (2017). Awareness, availability and accessibility of library resources by students of Kwara States, Melete. Nigeria. *Library Philosophy and Practice (e-journal)*. <https://digitalcommons.un/.edu/libphilprac/1629>.
- Ejikeme, A. N., & Okpala, H. N. (2017). Promoting children’s learning through technology literacy: challenges to school librarians in the 21st century. *Education and Information Technologies*, 22, 1163-1177.
- Eiriemiokhale, K. A. & Ibeun M. O. (2017). Awareness, availability and accessibility of library resources by students of Kwara States, Melete. Nigeria: *Library Philosophy and Practice*. <https://digitalcommons.un/.edu/libphilprac/1629>
- Federal Ministry of Education and Youth Development. (2019). Minimum standards for school libraries in Nigeria. Federal Ministry of Education. <https://education.gov.ng/>
- Fischer, G., Lundin, J., & Lindberg, J. O. (2020). Rethinking and reinventing learning, education and collaboration in the digital age— from creating technologies to transforming cultures. *Campus-wide Information Systems*, 37(5), 241–252. <https://doi.org/10.1108/ijilt-04-2020-0051>
- Fisher, D. & Frey, N. (2018). Raise reading volume through access, choice, discussion, and book talks. *The Reading Teacher* 72(1): 89–97.
- Flood, A. (2014). Readers absorb less on kindle than on paper, study finds. <http:// www.theguardian.com/books/2014/aug/19/readers-absorb-less-kindles-paper- study-plot-ereader-digitisation>
- Garcia, A., & Martinez, R. (2019). The impact of library service quality on borrowing rates: A case study of academic libraries in Spain. *Library Management*, 40(6/7), 521- 534.
- Gbemi-Ogunleye, P. (2016) Library Use and students academic achievement: implication for counseling. *Information and Knowledge Management*, 6, 50-52
- Goss, H. (2022). Student learning outcomes assessment in higher education and in academic libraries: A review of the literature. *The Journal of Academic Librarianship*, 48(2), 102485.
- Hair Jr, J. F., Black, W. C., Babin, B. J., & Anderson, R. E. (2013). *Multivariate data analysis (7th ed.)*. Pearson.
- Heritage, M. (2016). "Assessment for learning: co-regulation in and as student self- sssessment." *The Australian Educational Researcher*, 43(4), 477-491. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13384-016-0210-0>
- Hord, S. M., & Tobia, E. F. (2015). *Reclaiming out teaching profession: The power of educators learning in community*. Teachers College Press.
- Hunter, S. (2014). Correlates of school library in Calabar, Nigeria: Implications for counseling. *Journal of Education and Practice*, 2(12), 67-71.
- IFLA (2015). IFLA/UNESCO school library guidelines. <https://www.ifla.org/>
- Ikolo, V. E. (2015). Users Satisfaction with Library Services. *International Journal of Information and Communication Technology Education*, 11(2), 80–89. <https://doi.org/10.4018/ijicte.2015040107>
- Iosr, J., & Moruf, H. A. (2015). Students’ utilization of secondary school libraries in Akinyele Local Government Area of Oyo State, Nigeria. *Journal of Research & Method in Education*. <https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.1425377.v1>
- Iqbal, N., Jamil, F., Ahmad, S., & Kim, D. (2020). Toward effective planning and Management using predictive analytics based on rental book data of academic libraries. *Ieee Access*, 8, 81978-81996.
- Istifanus, I. L., Yohanna, P. M., & Usman, E. A. (2019). Availability, accessibility and utilization of information resources in school libraries in Maiduguri and Damaturu Metropolis, Nigeria. *Asian Journal of Information Science and Technology*, 9(2), 119–124. <https://doi.org/10.51983/ajist-2019.9.2.263>

- Jaja, C. A., & Udumukwu, I. J. (2023). Utilization of school library and students' academic achievement in Abuja Federal Capital Territory. *International Journal of Library and Information Science Studies*, 9(6), 61–72. <https://doi.org/10.37745/ijliss.15/vol9n66172>
- Jato, M., Ogunniyi, S. O., & Olubiyo, P. O. (2014). Study habits, use of school libraries and students academic performance in selected secondary schools in Ondo West Local Government Area of Ondo State. *International Journal of Library and Information Science*, 6(4), 57–64. <https://doi.org/10.5897/ijlis2012.0412>
- Junco, R., & Clem, C. (2015). Predicting course outcomes with digital textbook usage data. *The Internet and Higher Education*, 27, 54–63. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.iheduc.2015.06.001>
- Khan, S. A. (2017). Family book sharing practices and their influence on children's literacy development in Pakistan. *Journal of Research in Childhood Education*, 31(2), 187- 202.
- King'aru, M. J. (2014). Factors contributing to poor performance of science subject; A case of secondary schools in Kawe division, Kinondoni municipality, (Unpublished Doctoral dissertation). Open University of Tanzania.
- Li, H. (2020). The rise of digital book borrowing in China: A study of user preferences and library app functionalities. *Journal of Library and Information Services in Asia*, 11(2), 123-138.
- Liu, Q., Allard, B., Lo, P., Zhou, Q., Jiang, T., & Itsumura, H. (2019). Library user education as a window to understand inquiry-based learning in the context of higher education in Asia: A comparative study between Peking University and the University of Tsukuba. *College & Research Libraries*, 80(1), 8.
- Loewen, J. W. (2018). Teaching what “really” happened: how to avoid the tyranny of textbooks and get students excited about doing history (2nd ed.). *Multicultural Education Series*. In *Tyranny of Textbooks*. Teachers College Press. <https://eric.ed.gov/?id=ED592395>
- McIntosh, E. (2020). Relationship of middle school pupils' reading habits, text access, and library use with reading achievement (Doctoral dissertation, Fordham University).
- Merga, M. K., & Roni, S. M. (2018). Children's perceptions of the importance and value of reading. *Australian Journal of Education*, 62(2), 135–153. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0004944118779615>
- Moruf, H. A. (2015). Students' utilization of secondary school libraries in akinyele local government area of Oyo state. *Journal of Research & Method in Education*, 5(2), 60- 66.
- Mr, A., & Abel, K. (2016). School library media resources availability as a predictor of secondary school students academic achievement in social studies in Ondo State, Nigeria. *Library Philosophy and Practice*. <https://digitalcommons.unl.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=4025&context=libphilprac>
- MSEd, K. C. (2023, February 28). The sensorimotor stage of cognitive development. *Very well Mind*. <https://www.verywellmind.com/sensorimotor-stage-of-cognitive-development-2795462>
- Muendo, J. K. (2016). Influence of school infrastructural environment on performance in Kenya Certificate of Secondary Education In Kibauni Division Of Machakos Count, Kenya. University of Nairobi. <http://erepository.uonbi.ac.ke/handle/11295/97145>
- Muijs, D., & Reynolds, D. (2017). *Effective teaching: Evidence and practice*. Sage.
- Nguyen, T. H. (2021). The growing phenomenon of book cafes in Vietnam: Combining book borrowing with a cafe experience. *Public Library Quarterly*, 36(4), 381-392.
- O'Leary, E. S., Shapiro, C., Toma, S., Sayson, H. W., Levis-Fitzgerald, M., Johnson, T., & Sork, V. L. (2020). Creating inclusive classrooms by engaging STEM faculty in culturally responsive teaching workshops. *International Journal of STEM Education*, 7(1). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40594-020-00230-7>
- O'Leary, E.S., Shapiro, C., Toma, S., Sayson, H.W., Levis-Fitzgerald, M. & Johnson, T. (2020) Creating inclusive classrooms by engaging STEM faculty in culturally responsive teaching workshops. *International Journal of STEM Education*, 7(32). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40594-020-00230-7>
- Onifade, F. N., Ogbuiyi, S. U., & Omeluzor, S. U. (2013). Library resources and service utilization by postgraduate students in a Nigerian private university. *International Journal of Library and Information Science*, 5(9), 294–299. <https://doi.org/10.5897/ijlis.9000065>
- Onuoha, U. D. (2013). Undergraduates' use of libraries in federal universities in South- West, Nigeria. *IOSR Journal of Research & Method in Education*, 3(5), 12–17. <https://doi.org/10.9790/7388-0351217>
- Onwubiko, E. C. (2022). An assessment of the effect of self-efficacy, reading culture, utilization of library habits on the academic achievements of student- librarians. *Library Philosophy & Practice*, 5(3).
- Otiike, F., & Barátné, Á. H. (2021). Roles and emerging trends of academic libraries in Kenya. *Library Hi Tech News*, 38(7), 19–23.

<https://doi.org/10.1108/lhtn-09-2021-0058>

Owusu-Acheaw, M. (2014). Reading habits among students and its effect on academic performance: a study of students of Koforidua Polytechnic. *Library Philosophy and Practice*, 1. <https://digitalcommons.unl.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=2908&context=libphilprac>

Pakistyaningsih, A., Nurdyansyah, N., Arifin, M. B. U. B., Rudyanto, H. E., & Rais, P. (2019). School library utilization technology model to improve reading interest and reading ability in elementary education. *Universal Journal of Educational Research*, 7(9), 1945-1955

Rajaratnam, R. (2013). For the love of reading! new strategies to engage the next generation of readers. <http://library.ifla.org/71/1/105-rajaratnamen.pdf>

Rasheed, S. T., & Shoaga, O. (2019). The influence of home violence on psychosocial adjustment of unior Secondary School Pupils in Ijebu North Local Government, Ogun State Nigeria. *KIU Journal of Humanities*, 4(2), 135-139. <https://www.ijhumas.com/ojs/index.php/kiuhums/article/download/556/518>

Read, T. (2015). Where have all the textbooks gone?: Toward sustainable provision of teaching and learning materials in Sub-Saharan Africa. <https://doi.org/10.1596/978-1-4648-0572-1>

Resnick, L. B. (2017). Toward a cognitive theory of instruction. In *Learning and motivation in the classroom* (pp. 5-38). Routledge.

Riska, A. (2019). Pemanfaatan perpustakaan sekolah sebagai sumber belajar siswa SD inpres 12/79 biru II kecamatan tanete riattang kabupaten bone [Utilization of School Libraries as Learning Resources for Students of SD Inpres 12/79 BiruII, Tanete Riattang District, Bone Regency]. *JIKAP PGSD: Jurnal Ilmiah Ilmu Kependidikan*, 3(2), 165-175

Rose-Wiles, L. (2013). Are print books dead? An investigation of book circulation at a Mid-Sized Academic Library. *Technical Services Quarterly*, 30(2), 129-152. <https://doi.org/10.1080/07317131.2013.759496>

Rubin, R. E. (2017). *Foundations of library and information science*. American Library Association.

Shintia, D., Arafat, Y., & Setiawan, A. A. (2021). The influence of school library utilization and reading interest on student achievement. *Journal of Social Work and Science Education*, 2(2), 127-136.

Siguenza-Guzmán, L., Saquicela, V., Avila-Ordóñez, E., Vandewalle, J., & Cattrysse, D. (2015). Literature Review of Data mining Applications in Academic Libraries. *The Journal of Academic Librarianship*, 41(4), 499-510. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.acalib.2015.06.007>

Sparks, R. L., Patton, J., & Murdoch, A. (2013). Early reading success and its relationship to reading achievement and reading volume: replication of '10 years later.' *Reading and Writing*, 27(1), 189-211. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11145-013-9439-2>

Stemmer, J. K., & Mahan, D. M. (2016). Investigating the relationship of library usage to student outcomes. *College & Research Libraries*, 359-375. doi:10.5860/crl.77.3.359

Stemmer, J., & Mahan, D. M. (2016). Investigating the relationship of library usage to student outcomes. *College & Research Libraries*, 77(3), 359-375. <https://doi.org/10.5860/crl.77.3.35>

Suleiman, Y., Hanafi, Z., & Tanslikhan, M. (2018). Perceived influence of library services on students' academic achievement in secondary schools in Kwara State, Nigeria. *Library Philosophy and Practice*, 1. <https://digitalcommons.unl.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=4934&context=libphilprac>

Suleiman, Y., Hanafi, Z., & Tanslikhan, M. (2018). Perceived influence of library services on students academic achievement in secondary schools in Kwara State, Nigeria. *Library Philosophy and Practice (e-journal)*, 1744.

Ternenge T. S., & Agipu, O. L. (2019). Availability and utilization of school library resources in selected secondary schools in Makurdi Metropolis. *Library Philosophy and Practice*. <https://digitalcommons.unl.edu/libphilprac/2542>.

Thomas, G., Morgan, K., & Harris, K. (2016). Albert Bandura. *Learning in sports coaching: Theory and application*, 22-33.

Tran, T., Lê, T. T. H., Nguyen, T. T. T., Pham, A. G., Vu, T. H., Nguyễn, M. H., Vuong,

H. M., Vuong, T. T., Hoang, P. H., Ho, M., & Vuong, Q. (2019). The relationship between birth order, sex, home scholarly culture and youths' reading practices in promoting lifelong learning for sustainable development in Vietnam. *Sustainability*, 11(16), 4389. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su11164389>

Venegas, E. M. (2018). Strengthening the reader self-efficacies of reluctant and struggling readers through literature circles. *Reading & Writing Quarterly*, 34(5), 419-435.

Wang, J., Zheng, L., Alsulami, H., & Chen, J. (2022). Modeling and analysis of the book borrowing of students in the library using

partial differential equations. *Fractals*, 30(2)

Affiliations and Corresponding Information

Maylene F. Grigana, RL, LPT

Department of Education – Philippines

Anna Liza C. Cerbo, PhD

Cor Jesu College – Philippines